

Teachers' Professional Qualification as a Critical Predictor of Learners Academic Achievement in Inclusive Primary Schools

Submitted: 10.10.2021

Abstract

The paper established the relationship between teachers' professional qualification and learners' academic achievement in public inclusive primary schools in Kakamega County. This study was informed by the social learning theory of Albert Bandura and adopted a mixed research design. A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted. Schools as units of the study were sampled using stratified random sampling and purposive sampling technique with 12 Sub-counties as the strata. Simple random sampling techniques was used to select 826 standards 7 learners while purposive sampling was used to select 33 deputy head teachers, 31 class teachers and 4 Educational Assessment and Resource Centre coordinators. Census sampling was used to select 1 County Director of Education. The total sample size for the study was 899 respondents. Questionnaires, interview schedule, observation check lists, document analysis guide and focus group discussions were used to collect data. Findings showed that the qualifications of teachers are statistically substantial predictor of learners' academic performance It is recommended that the Government of Kenya should train more teachers in special needs education on how to use relevant resources during teaching. It is hoped that the study findings might add to the existing knowledge base in the area of inclusive education.

Keywords: Academic Achievement, Disabilities, Inclusive Education, Teachers' Qualification

1.1 Introduction

Inclusive education is about embracing all (NCF-2005). It has been internationally recognized as a philosophy for attaining equity, justice and quality education for all children, especially those who have been traditionally excluded from mainstream education among others: differently abled children or gifted children, street or working children, children from remote or nomadic populations, children belonging to ethnic, linguistic or cultural minorities or children from other disadvantaged or marginalized groups. According to UNESCO it is a process of addressing and responding to the diverse needs of all learners by increasing participation in learning and reducing exclusion within and from education. This means that all children have the right to a quality education that caters, to the extent possible, to their individual needs.

An inclusive class may have amongst others people with or without disabilities being able to learn together in ordinary preschool provisions, schools, and community educational settings with an appropriate network of support service. Schools need to become a center that prepares children for life and ensure that all children, especially the differently able children from marginalized sections (NCF, 2005). In overall terms, Inclusive education implies four key elements: it is a process of looking for the most appropriate ways of responding to diversity as well as trying to learn how to learn from the differences; it is stimulating through multiple strategies, the creativity and the capacity of addressing and resolving problems of students; it comprises the right of the child to attend school, express his/her opinion, have quality learning experiences and attain valuable learning outcomes; and it implies the moral responsibility of prioritizing those students who are at risk of being marginalized and excluded from the school, and of obtaining low learning outcomes.

To date, some countries have been successful in promoting inclusive education practices and policies that remove barriers and create conditions which enable all children to learn. However, in poorer developing countries, the process of creating an inclusive system is more difficult. Factors such as lack of available funding, administrative and policy level support, and trained personnel pose challenges that can slow down progress. As a result of these difficulties, some countries may choose to begin the process by first focusing on one group of children with the long-term goal of eventually including all excluded groups

Widely acknowledged in all settings, is that teachers are key to success in inclusion since they need to be sensitive to the needs of students and the environment. For a smooth transition from mainstream education to inclusive education, the role of the teacher in a changing environment has also required a change. A change will not yield the desired results if those who implement it are resistant or are not committed. Specifically, teachers are required to reconsider their roles, construct new knowledge and learn new skills to equip themselves for the change. Teachers may need to acquire new skills and reject some of their beliefs and practices. According to Mastropieri & Scruggs, (2010) teachers play a pivotal role in mainstreaming inclusive education.

No matter how excellent the educational infrastructure might be, how well articulated educational policy might be, how well resourced a program might be, effective inclusion does not take place until regular classroom teachers deliver relevant and meaningful instruction to students with disabilities. The teacher has to provide holistic support and focused involvement with the children with special needs based on a joint perspective, mutual understanding, and networking. Teachers with the support of the principal of the school, colleagues, special educators and parents should develop effective ways of overcoming barriers to learning. The inclusion of differently able students in regular education classrooms requires regular school teachers to upgrade their skills in-order to respond to the new challenges provided by their changing roles and responsibilities. These teachers are now expected to address problems and provide solutions to challenges posed by special needs students who may vary in their skill levels.

Inclusion requires a large vision and specific competencies for teachers. The teachers need to know that diversity is present in the classroom and that they should attend to diverse needs. Three important educational aspects that every teacher must know to be inclusive: Equality: Promoting the same opportunities for all. Quality: Offering functional and meaningful learning. Equity: Responding to special educational needs. In inclusive education, the school and classrooms are very dynamic and have a lot of interactions and roles. Recognizing that the other, is not a continuation of me, but has its own view leads teachers to explain, interpret and act from their point of view. This vision then transforms from two ideas (you and me) to a new figure (us).

Kochhar and West (1996) laid stress that, in inclusive education classrooms regular school teachers are required to teach 'content' differently. It must be integrative, flexible and interdisciplinary. In contrast to the traditional classroom now the focus shifts from

teaching to learning. Teachers are now required to create situations in which a student's learning is maximized. The regular classroom teacher is now viewed as a 'thoughtful professional', one who is able to understand the relationship between teaching and learning. Thus the roles and responsibilities of regular school teachers have now been comprehensive. It is therefore vital that regular school teachers have the appropriate knowledge, skills, and attitudes to fulfill their new roles and responsibilities.

As Hargreaves and Fullan (1992) state, better expertise in classroom management so that more time can be provided to instruction; knowing how to teach mixed-ability classes; increasing awareness and becoming proficient in new teaching strategies like cooperative learning or 'whole language' approaches to learning; and able to respond to the different learning styles of their pupils – attention to all these things can certainly help teachers increase their pupils opportunities to learn. According to Mastropieri & Scruggs (2010), regular school teachers should know about the learning styles and the motivational patterns of differently able children. The teachers must have an understanding of the resources available to help them in working with students with disabilities. They should present information to the students in a manner which enables them to assimilate the information easily.

Vaughn & Bos (2012) suggested a number of strategies that regular school teachers would require in order to accommodate students with disabilities in the classroom environment. These include peer tutoring, mastery learning, cooperative learning, and applied behavior analysis. The Council for Exceptional Children (2010) developed and validated a common core of minimum essential knowledge and skills necessary for entry into professional practice in special education. 'It includes – philosophical, historical and legal foundations of special education; characteristics of learners; assessment, diagnosis, and evaluation; instructional content and practice; planning and managing the learning environment; managing student behavior and social interaction skills; communication and collaborative partnerships and; professionalism and ethical practices.' While all of these skills may not be needed for regular classroom teachers, a certain level of ability in these competencies, however, is required from these teachers when they are expected to work with special needs children.

Teaching Competencies in Inclusive Classroom

There are some competencies that are field tested and supported as probable methods for delivering effective instruction to students with diverse learning needs. These are:

Believing in Students: A teacher must believe in the student's possibilities and support systems with a clear vision that all children can learn. In this way, she will help in preventing the barriers and limitations of learning that could marginalize children and young people from their potential. It also includes learning conception, individual differences, the values of solidarity, respect, and collaboration. The inclusive teacher should recognize individual differences and participate in collective teaching because it is essential in implementing education of diversity. The inclusive teacher should have a holistic educational view with strong skills and experience in order to participate in diverse contexts.

Knowledge of Terminology of Inclusive Education: Knowledge in the context of inclusive education includes a knowledge and understanding of basic terminology and concepts used in special education; history of inclusive education; policies, programs and legislation related to inclusive education; rights, roles and responsibilities of parents, students, teachers and other professionals. **Cooperation from Other Staff:** An ever-increasing diversity in the classrooms has made it necessary for regular classroom teachers to work with special education teachers, school psychologists, professionals (such as speech and language therapists, occupational therapists, physiotherapists, recreational therapists etc.) parents of students with disabilities etc. This will help in having fewer problems and this will be an effective method to utilize each teacher's strengths.

Skills of Classroom Management: Along with the psycho-social environment, the physical aspects of the classroom also exert a great influence on the inclusive classroom environment. The physical environment comprises of aspects such as an arrangement of desks, lighting, and temperature. Thus a teacher must have knowledge of classroom management theories, methods, and techniques for individuals with different learning needs; research-based best practices for effective management of teaching and learning; materials arrangement creating a positive atmosphere in the classroom and organization of aids and support services.

Techniques of Assessment: Assessment -formal and informal is one of the most vital skills for a regular classroom teacher to have in the implementation of inclusive education programs. The teacher has to employ both, basic skills such as gathering, learning, and background information of differently able students and also highly specialized skills such as selecting, administering, scoring and interpreting standardized measurement instruments. She has to evaluate three aspects of differently able students' performance while evaluating their success in inclusion programs-performance, attitudes, and process. Performance measures student's achievement in content areas. Attitude measures differently able student's self-concept and their attitudes toward their teachers and non-disabled peers. Process measures the types of interactions differently able students have with their teachers and peers. Thus performance-based assessments, portfolios and curriculum-based assessments are to be used by the teacher.

Techniques of Instructions: A number of specific instructional techniques that regular classroom teachers would require to be competent to include -activity based and peer tutoring, experiential learning, and collaborative learning. With the use of both activity-based and experiential learning, students become involved in the discovery, interaction with the environment and manipulation of materials. As this learning uses real-life activities and materials, skill generalization and transfer are facilitated. Peer tutoring is another instructional strategy that involves student partnerships, involving high achievers with lower achievers. Peer tutoring has been found to minimize problem behaviors, increase opportunities to respond and improve activity comprehension (Marchand-Martella & Martella, 1993). Cooperative learning encourages students to work together to complete tasks and solve problems. The teachers need to specify each student's role for the task, clarify the sequence of activities and monitor and evaluate the interactions between the group members. Putnam, (1998) these approaches enhance learning, improve inter-group relations, develop problem-solving skills and improve the academic and social skills of students with special needs in regular education classrooms.

Individualized Instruction: Individualized instructions are educational approaches that recognize, anticipate and program for variation according to the student's background knowledge, learning styles, motivation and personal interest. Creating an educational program that is tailored to the unique needs of a differently able child is the hallmark of special education. This is what makes special education different from regular education. However, a union of both well-established stream of instruction is needed from regular

school teachers if they are to serve all students in their classrooms including those with exceptionality. It requires teachers to implement alternative teaching actions such as modifying assignments, materials, testing procedures, grading criteria and varying presentation styles in order to improve the achievement of differently able students in regular education classrooms. Teachers can also accommodate variations in learning styles by using a variety of environmental, physical, social and psychological conditions.

Use of Technology: Use of technology for special needs students has made it possible for to accomplish a number of tasks while being in a regular education environment that was not possible earlier. Apart from the "traditional" knowledge and skill domains, regular school teachers are now also expected to demonstrate ability in the use of technology. To sum up, equity and integration of education for these students do not only mean to simply enroll them into regular schools or classrooms. It means that physical and psychological barriers between these children and the others are broken. Teachers in the traditional mode are likely to view these children — incapable, difficult to handle, or merely worthy of segregation into special schools. These children require physical and emotional acceptance at home and at school. They need a flexible curriculum, barrier-free classroom or school environment, modified schemes of examination and teaching practices, adapted teaching aids and above all-a sensitive teacher. It is necessary that teachers take the responsibility for improving the learning and involvement of all children in their classes. For this, teachers need to develop competencies that comprise knowledge & skills to teach equitably and to encourage the learning of all pupils. Moreover, teachers need to be able to pursue and practice the support of other people who can serve as valuable resources in inclusive education, such as support staff, parents, communities, school authorities and not to miss the relevant others. Teachers can be benefited by the approach of Inclusive education in various ways. Inclusive education can be achieved in the true sense by understanding the diversity of individual human being, recognizing that all students have strengths and potential, the significance of individualized instruction, ways of creatively addressing challenges, problem-solving skills and skills related to teamwork.

1.2 Inclusive Education in Kenya

While inclusive education has been implemented successfully in many countries, in Kenya just as in other developing countries, the process of achieving this goal is still work in progress. Inclusive education in Kenya is characterized by mainstreaming children with disabilities into regular classroom settings, allowing them to learn together with their non-disabled peers. Ideally, the Government of Kenya (GoK) recognizes that inclusive education brings joy and happiness to the life of children, promotes social justice and equity. It is committed to provision of inclusive, relevant and equitable quality education and training opportunities to all its citizens. This is manifest in Kenya's bold declarations and ratification of various international frameworks and the development of laws and policies geared towards fulfilling the fundamental human right to education (Republic of Kenya, 2013). It is imperative to note that in Kenya, key education stakeholders have consistently recognized the importance of education and training for persons with disabilities.

The Ominde Commission (Republic of Kenya, 1964) pointed out that there was need for training teachers in special education and establishing special schools. It recommended the need to offer teacher trainees courses on how to integrate children with mild impairments in regular schools. Inclusive education, which includes intensive practice of modern schools, now poses many complex issues and challenges. Today demands specialists with not only deep knowledge and skills in the field of education, owning a modern interactive teaching methods and education of children, but also personality, patience and tolerance for people, regardless of their physical and other features. Preparation of the modern teacher, able to implement inclusive education is extremely relevant and challenging for higher pedagogical school. It is a content-ideological, moral and spiritual training of professionals in the humanities, the ability to independently and creatively, it is advisable to choose and use technologies which are appropriate for use with specific educational groups, whether children with physical and intellectual disabilities, children from different social groups living in the city or village.

That same year, the government appointed the committee on care and rehabilitation of the disabled, chaired by Ngala Mwendwa (Republic of Kenya, 1964a). This committee made various recommendations on rehabilitation and education of persons with disabilities in Kenya. The National Committee on Educational Objectives (Gachathi

report) (Republic of Kenya, 1976) delved into the issue of special needs education (SNE) and provided significant recommendations, for example, on early identification and placement, integration of learners into regular schools and provision of regular curriculum. Major developments emanating from the report were the establishment of pre-primary classes in special schools, assessment centers and the establishment of the Kenya Institute of Special Education (KISE). Other commissions that made significant contributions to SNE were the Presidential Working Party on Education and Manpower Training for the Next Decade and Beyond (Kamunge Commission) (Republic of Kenya, 1988), and the commission of Inquiry into the Education System in Kenya (Koech Commission) (Republic of Kenya, 1999). These commissions guided the management of SNE, training of teachers on special education, development of appropriate curricula, adapting examinations to suit learners and trainees with special needs, and the inclusion of emerging areas such as education of the gifted and talented, those with specific learning difficulties and those with communication difficulties. However, there was no specific policy on special education; the government was relying on circulars until the SNE Policy Framework was developed in 2009 and revised in 2018.

1.3 Statement of the Problem

The MoE reports indicate that teachers have been trained to adequately assist learners with SEN in schools (MoE, 2008, Wango, 2011). Despite the training of teachers in SNE, the access and retention rates of learners with SEN in public inclusive primary schools are still very low. The situation is alarming in Kakamega County where some learners with SEN cannot access and participate in free inclusive primary education. Reports indicate that despite the Free Primary Education to enhance inclusive education, there is an increase in primary school dropout rates (MoEST, 2012). Another report by MoEST (2015) also indicates that the enrolment of disabled learners at lower classes is usually 1.5 % that of the entire school enrolment. However, more than ½ % of the disabled learners do not sit for Kenya Certificate of Primary Education (KCPE) or if they sit KCPE their scores are always below average. Records at the Kakamega County Assessment and Resource Centre (EARC) show that a very small number of learners with disabilities have been assessed and placed in inclusive primary schools yet they are never retained in schools to complete the primary education cycle.

1.4 Objective of the Study

The objective of this study was:

To establish the link between teachers' professional qualification and learners academic achievement in primary schools in Kakamega County, Kenya

1.5 Methodology

This study adopted a mixed research approach that yielded both qualitative and quantitative data. It catered for multiple forms of data collection such as observations, interviews and FGD (qualitative data) with traditional surveys as quoted by Creswell (2015). Mixed methods research has two distinct characteristics. Data is collected in both qualitative and quantitative form (Creswell, 2015; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2011; Hesse-Biber, 2010; Jonson, Onwuegbuzie, & Turner, 2007). Early methods of collecting data had bias and weaknesses and so mixed method research neutralized the weaknesses of each form of data. It involves triangulating data sources thus a means for seeking convergence across qualitative and quantitative method (Clough & Nutbrown, 2012). Clough & Nutbrown indicate that mixed research methods are complementary to one another whereby the strengths of one method is complement for the weakness of another. Mixed methods approach report results or findings of the study that are both inductive and deductive in nature (Creswell, 2015), presents data that are both numerical and textual in nature (Bazeley, 2009; Creswell & Plano, 2011). Kasunic (2000) describes the purpose of triangulation as being to obtain confirmation of finding through convergence of different perspectives. In triangulation qualitative and quantitative data are collected concurrently in one phase as opined by Creswell (2015). In this study the data was collected concurrent. The researcher collected survey data using questionnaires and interviews data at the same time and compared results. The method was used to confirm, cross validate or corroborate findings (Bazeley, 2018). It was deemed useful in expanding quantitative

data through collection of open-ended qualitative data. As explained by Mertler & Charles (2011); Cohen, Manion, & Morrison (2018) the researcher does not manipulate the variables under study but instead, examines the variables in their existing condition. Therefore, the researcher conducted the study within the then existing implementation of inclusive education in the study area. A mixed method research design is sufficient in collecting large amounts of information within the shortest time (Mertler, 2018). The design can be used when collecting information about people's attitudes, opinions, habits or any of the variety of education or social issues (Leedy & Ormrod, 2013).

A mixed research design was useful in this study as the intention was to establish effectiveness of implementing inclusive education on learners' academic performance in inclusive primary schools in a number of ways. This design allowed the researcher to collect data from a large sample of learners, teachers, and education officers using questionnaires; interview guides, document analysis guide and observation check lists. It was considered appropriate for the study because the study focused on the observations, opinions and perceptions of the then existing situation. The design suited the study for its effectiveness in collecting data and describing the implementation of inclusive education practices in the real situations on the ground. The study gathered facts, knowledge, opinions and judgment from teachers, deputy head teachers, learners and education officers on how they viewed and implemented inclusive education in regard to learners' academic performance in Public primary schools. The learners' cognitive, social and personal competencies were of interest by the research because they contribute to learners' academic performance. The design allowed collection of both qualitative and quantitative data that was subjected to both descriptive and inferential analysis.

1.6 Study Population and Sampling

Study population comprised of 2,772 standards seven learners, 104 class teachers and 106 deputy head teachers drawn from 104 public primary schools. Twelve EARC Coordinators and one County director of education also formed part of the population. Table 1 shows sampling frame and sample size.

Table 1: Sampling Frame and Sample Size

Category of Participants	Population	Sample size	Percentage (%)	Sampling Techniques
Learners	2772	826	30	Purposive, Stratified random
Class teachers	104	31	30	Purposive
Deputy head teachers	106	33	30	Purposive
EARC Coordinators	12	4	30	Purposive
C.D.E	1	1	100	Census
Total	2995	899	30%	

Source: Researcher, 2017

From Table 1, schools were sampled using stratified random sampling technique along geographical lines, with 12 Sub-counties as the strata. Stratified random sampling is a process in which certain subgroups referred to as strata are selected for inclusion in a sample (Mertler, 2018). Only schools practicing inclusive education were purposively selected in each stratum. Given that categories of public primary schools according to the Ministry of education, Kenya are; boys boarding, girls boarding, mixed day and mixed boarding, to further obtain a representation of the categories of schools from the strata, the researcher purposively selected at least 2 schools from each category from each stratum to be represented in the sample. Given that not all the 4 categories were found in all sub-counties, the researcher purposively selected from the category of schools found within the sub-county. For example, in Mumias sub-county in all-inclusive schools (38) there were all 4 categories of schools thus; 1 boys' boarding, 1 girls boarding', 1 mixed

boarding and majority (35) were mixed day. In this case of Mumias sub-county each category was selected basing on the availability of number of schools in each category to be represented in the sample as follows; 1 boys' boarding, 1 girls boarding' 1 mixed boarding and 2 mixed day schools giving a total of 5 schools sampled in the sub-county.

1.7 Research Instruments

The researcher used triangulation method of data collection which involved more than one instrument to collect data. Edwards, (2010) argues that no single method of collecting data is perfect; therefore, using more than one method is recommended. Five data collection instruments were used to collect data to meet the objectives of the study. These were focused group discussion guide (FGD) with learners, questionnaires for teachers and learners, structured interview schedule for class teachers, observation schedules and document analysis schedules.

1.8 Pilot Study

The pilot study enabled the determination of purposive sample units for the main research, to develop, modify and check the feasibility of the instruments and to determine how large the final sample needed to be. The pilot study covered 10% of the target population which was within 3 schools. That was 3 teachers, 3 deputy head teachers and 37 learners drawn from 3 public inclusive schools. The schools and respondents used in the pilot study were excluded from the final study. The instruments were revised as per the results of the pilot study. For example, following item revision, the item "To what extent do you agree to your teacher use of individual teaching in school?" from the original scale was changed to "To what extent do you agree to the use of one teacher supporting one child's ability at a time during learning?" This was after some learners misinterpreted to mean one learner in a class at a time.

1.9 Study Location

The study was conducted in public inclusive primary schools in Kakamega County. The County is located on the western part of Kenya. The county is made up of 12 sub-Counties namely; Mumias, Matungu, Kakamega Central, Navakholo, Khwisero, Butere, Kakamega North, Kakamega South, Kakamega East, Likuyani, Lugari and Matete. The region is located between 1° 15' North and 0° 3' West longitude and to the East 35° 12' East longitude (ROK, 2003). The total area of the County is about 3,244.9 SQ KM² (ROK, 2003). This area is about 1.4% of the total area of Kenya. The county has a population of 1,660,651 people as per the 2009 population census (ROK, 2010). This presents 11.23%, of the total Kenyan population. The average population density is 515 persons per km². The population growth has fluctuated between 3.4 in 1969 and 0.3 in 2014 (Rok, 2015). Unfortunately, 57% of the populations live below the poverty line.

The County receives heavy rains and it is fertile. Indigenous people speak Luhya language, although there are varieties of dialects. The County has mineral production potential such as gold mining. It is enriched with Kakamega forest which attracts tourists. Economic activities practiced mainly include farming of maize, sugarcane and tea among others. They also practice animal farming such as dairy and poultry farming. Trade is also practiced. Illicit brews such as Chang'aa and Busaa' (traditional liquor) is prohibited in Kenyan government yet, to most of the people in the entire region of the County have ventured in it as one of the economic activities to fight poverty. In turn it has resulted into drug abuse even among school going children. This is evident especially in Kakamega North which has contributed to high school dropout rate that has affected the academic performance for years. According to Luhya culture, it is mandatory for boys to be circumcised before marriage. Failure to adhere to it is considered an abomination. For boys with severe disabilities never undergo such rites of passage hence they face two

challenges; stigmatization for having disability and being an abomination to the society. Communities living around Kakamega forest such as the Tiriki and Nandi hide persons with disabilities in their houses and when these persons with disabilities become sick, they are taken to Kakamega forest to die there (EARC-Kakamega, 2014). Perceptions regarding persons with disabilities over the years were as hopeless and useless (Munyi, 2012). However, Munyi further noted that, in the field of education, perceptions towards persons with disability had changed significantly and the challenge to educators was to ensure that schools were readily and accessible to persons with disabilities and the regular learners.

1.8 Findings and Discussion

The null hypothesis: H_0 : There is no relationship between teachers' professional qualification and learners' academic achievement was tested. A simple linear regression was conducted using teachers' qualification at five levels as the independent variable while academic achievement operationalized as learners' scores on end-term examination as dependent variable.

The underlying assumptions of regression were tested (linear relationship in the data, homoscedasticity and normality of residuals), using scatter plot, Q-Q plot (Appendix (i) and histograms (Appendix 2). The scatter plot revealed a linear relationship in the data which allowed us to conduct a linear regression analysis. The histogram indicated that the residuals approximate a normal distribution. The Q-Q-Plot of z^*_{pred} and $z^*_{preside}$ shows us that in our linear regression analysis there is no tendency in the error terms. To understand the data, descriptive statistics and correlations were also conducted and are presented in Table 2

Table 2: Results Showing Means, Standard Deviations and Correlations between the Variables

	Descriptive Statistics		Correlations		
	M	SD	N	Academ Achieve	AcademQual
Academ Achieve	281.03	23.475	30	1.000	0.542*
AcademQual	2.90	1.242	30	-	1.000

* Correlation significant at $\alpha=0.005$

Results in Table 2, reveal a positive and moderate correlation between academic achievement and teachers' level of qualification. Results of regression analysis indicated in the Model summary and overall fit statistics that the adjusted R^2 of the model was -269 with R^2 as -294. This meant that the linear regression explains 26.9% of the variance in the data. The Durbin-Watson $d = 0.874$, which is outside the two critical values of $1.5 < d < 2.5$ and therefore we can assume that there was first order linear auto-correlation in the data.

Table 3: F-Test showing the Relationship between the Variables

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4694.756	1	4694.756	11.647	.002 ^b
	Residual	11286.210	28	403.079		
	Total	15980.967	29			

a. Dependent Variable: academic achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), academic qualification(s)

The ANOVA Table (Table 3) showing the F-test which tests the null hypothesis that there is no linear relationship between the two variables (in other words $R^2=0$). With $F = 11.65$ and 29 degrees of freedom the test is highly significant ($p=0.002$), thus we can assume that there is a linear relationship between the variables in our model.

Regression analysis by SPSS also produces an output showing the regression coefficients, the intercept and the significance of all coefficients and the intercept in the model. These are presented in Table 4

Table 4: Regression Analysis Showing Standardized Coefficients and t-test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
1	(Constant)	251.313	9.448	26.598	.000	
	academic qualification(s)	10.248	3.003	.542	3.413	.002

a. Dependent Variable: academic achievement

From Table 4, the linear regression equation will be $Y = 251.3 - 10.25 X$, where Y Academic Achievement and X is Teachers' Qualification, the t-test shows that both intercept and variable academic qualification of teachers are highly significant ($t=26.59$, $p < 0.001$ for intercept and $t=3.41$, $p=0.002$ for the variable). This implies that variables are different from zero.

In Table 4, we also got the standardized Beta weights that show the relative importance of independent variables. In this study we had only one independent variable. So we conclude that academic qualifications of teachers are a statistically significant predictor of pupils' academic achievement ($\beta = 0.542$, $t=3.41$, $p=0.002$), we reject the null hypothesis that states; there is no relationship between teachers' qualification and learners' academic achievement in favor of the alternative. This finding may mean that when teachers have the requisite qualifications, they will have the pedagogical content knowledge to influence pupils' academic outcomes in an inclusive school.

Qualitatively the findings were coded, categorized and are reported in an emergent theme:

1.9 Emergent Theme: Discrepancies in Learners Academic Achievement

From document analysis and interviews, data revealed that six hundred and fifty (78.3%) of learners without disabilities are perceived by teachers as successful in academic classes. However, learners with disabilities fail to meet teachers' expectations in general education academic classes. Teachers noted that disability category is a significant factor in explaining variations in both scores and skill discrepancies. Learners with mental retardation, autism, traumatic brain injury, or multiple disabilities all tend to have higher scores than peers with learning disabilities. Mark lists revealed that learners who were reported to have emotional behavior disorders received lower scores than do learners whose disability profiles were physical. From the EARC offices records on learners' dropout rates were available and presented in Table 5

Table 5: Enrolment and Dropout rates of learners with disabilities

Year	No of learners assessed and placed in inclusive schools	Learners who dropped out	Highest marks out of 500 marks(KCPE)
2011	271	113	137
2012	267	73	141
2013	289	27	182
2014	311	38	198
2015	372	27	193
Total	1510	278	

Source: Researcher, 2017.

From Table 5, in the year 2011, two hundred and seventy-one (271) learners with disabilities were assessed at EARC and placed in inclusive schools to learn and in the same year 113 learners with disabilities dropped out of schools while for them that sat for KCPE, the highest mark score by a learner with learning disability was 137 marks out

of the possible 500 marks. The same trend repeated in the following 5 years. For example, in the year 2015, 372 learners with disabilities were assessed and placed in inclusive schools, however, in the same year, 27 learners with disabilities in all the twelve categories of disabilities dropped out of school while for those that sat for KCPE, the highest marks scored by a learner with learning disability was 193 out of 500 (38.6%).

From the trend one would note that, in all the 5 years the researcher captured the data learners with disabilities are assessed and placed in schools. At the same time there are those who drop out of school without completing the primary education cycle. Academically for the 5 years, there is a clear indication that the learners with disabilities happened to score below average marks in KCPE. The study considered this finding as crucial because IE is in place, but it is not fully actualized by implementers to minimize dropout rates of learners with disabilities. Similarly, scores for the learners with disabilities are low; below average in all the 5 years.

Teachers reported that almost $\frac{1}{4}$ of learners with disabilities in the classes perform satisfactorily well in academics. However, the teachers indicated that those learners with specific learning disabilities and emotional disturbed behaviors perform below average and affect school programs. Deputy Head teachers indicated that learners with disabilities and had abilities excelled both academically and socially irrespective of the disability. The finding confirms that learners with specific learning difficulties were considered not to perform satisfactorily because of communication difficulties while learners with physical disabilities and visual impairment were considered to perform well in KCPE (EARC, 2011). However, one can argue that the other categories of disabilities can also perform well if curriculum and examinations are adapted and assistive devices used to enable them function normally.

The finding concurs with what earlier scholars; Walton (2015), Srivastava, Boer & Pijl (2015), and Orodho (2013) who found out that qualified or trained staff was a one of the prerequisite factor for implementing inclusive education. The scholars noted that teachers who are not trained in special and inclusive education and who are unwilling or unenthusiastic about working with different abilities of children are a major barrier to inclusion. In the same vein, (UNESCO, 2010) posits that inadequate training of teachers in special and inclusive education impedes implementation of inclusive education.

The general finding was that, from the responses there is a clear indication that teacher qualification is a factor for implementing inclusive education. Hence, there is need for teachers to undergo training in SNE or IE to gain pedagogical content knowledge and skills to influence pupils' academic outcomes in inclusive schools. Teachers themselves should take an initiative to train and acquire skills in handling diversity of learners in classes.

1.10 Conclusions

From a regression analysis by SPSS produced an output showing the regression coefficients, the intercept and the significance of all coefficients and the intercept in the model. These were the linear regression equation was $Y = 251.3 + 10.25 X$, where Y Academic Achievement and X was teachers' qualification, the t-test showed that both intercept and variable academic qualification of teachers are highly significant ($t=26.59$, $p < 0.001$ for intercept and $t=3.41$, $p=0.002$ for the variable). This implies that variables are different from zero. We also got the standardized Beta weights that showed the relative importance of independent variables. So we concluded that academic qualifications of teachers are a statistically significant predictor of pupils' academic achievement ($\beta = 0.542$, $t=3.41$, $p=0.002$), we reject the null hypothesis that states; there is no relationship between teachers' qualification and learners' academic achievement in favor of the alternative.

This finding may mean that when teachers have the requisite qualifications, they will have the pedagogical content knowledge to influence pupils' academic outcomes in inclusive schools.

From document analysis, findings revealed that learners without disabilities are perceived by teachers as successful in academic classes. However, majority of learners with disabilities fail to meet teachers' expectations in general education academic classes. From the teachers, disability category is a significant factor in explaining variations in both scores and skill discrepancies. The teachers indicated that learners with mental retardation, autism, traumatic brain injury, or multiple disabilities all tend to have higher scores than peers with learning disabilities.

1.11 Recommendations

Following the above findings the study makes the following recommendations:

- i. The Government of Kenya and the Ministry of Education should review the training of primary school teachers so as to train all primary school teachers in the area of special needs education to empower teachers with skills and knowledge to teach inclusive classes.
- ii. Through seminars, workshops, and induction programmes, the Ministry of education need to develop in-service programmes for the old employed teachers, newly deployed head teachers and deputy head teachers.

References

Bazeley, P. (2009). Mixed methods data analysis. In S. Andrew & E. Halcomb (eds.), *Mixed Method Research for Nursing and Health Sciences* (pp.84-118). Chichester, UK: wily

- Bazeley, P. (2018). A mixed methods way of thinking and doing: integration of diverse perspectives in practice. *Journal on international studies*, 4, 17-28
- Clough, P. & Nutbrown. (2012). *A Student Guide to Methodology*, 3rd edition. London: DSage
- Cohen, L., Manion, L. & Morrison, K. (2018). *Research methods in education*. London: Routledge
- Creswell, J. W. (2015) *Qualitative inquiry and research design: choosing among five approaches*, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publications
- Creswell, J.W. & Clark, V.L.P. (2011). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research*. London: Sage.
- Council for Exceptional Children.(2010). Retrieved from <https://www.cec.sped.org/>
- EARC (2014). Report on learners with Special Needs. Kakamega.
- Edwards, A (2010). Qualitative research designs and analysis', in G. MacNaughton, S. Rolfe and I. Sire-Blatchford (eds). *Doing Early Childhood Research: International perspectives on theory and practice*, (2nd edition). Maidenhead: Open University press.
- Hargreaves., Fullan. (2004). Inclusive and exclusive educational change: emotional responses of teachers and implications for leadership. *School Leadership & Management*, 24(2)
- Hesse-Biber .S. (2010). *Qualitative Approaches to mixed methods Practice*. SAGE Publications.
- Johnson B.R., Onwuegbuzie and Turner. L. A (2007). Towards a Definition of Mixed Methods Research: *Journal of Mixed Methods Research*. SAGE Publications.
- Kasunic (2000). *Research Methods for Business. A skill Building Approach*: Uma Sekaran Southern Illinois University at Carbondale.
- Kochhar. A, Carol., Lynda L. West., & Juliana M. Taymans.(2000). Successful Inclusion: Practical Strategies for a Shared Responsibility. Retrieved from <https://www.pearson.com/us/higher-education/program/KochharSuccessful-Inclusion-Practical-Strategies-for-a-Shared-Responsibility-2nd-Edition/PGM121987.html>

Leedy, P.D., & Ormrod, J.E (2013). *Practical research: Planning and design* (10th ed.) Boston, MA: Allyn & Bacon.

Martella, Nancy, Marchand., Ronald, C. Martella, Matthew, Orlob., Tara Ebey.(2017). Conducting Action Research in a Rural High School Setting Using Peers as Corrective Reading Instructors for Students with Disabilities. *Rural Special Education*, 29, (4), 5-13.

Mastropieri, Margo, A., Thomas, E. Scruggs.(2010). *The Inclusive Classroom: Strategies for Effective Differentiated Instruction*. Retrieved from

Movkebaieva, Zulfija., Oralkanova, Indira., Uaidullakyzy, Elmira.(2013). The professional competence of teachers in inclusive education. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 89, 549 – 554. 136

Nandini, N., Haseen, Taj. (2014). Inclusive Education: Key Role of teachers for its Success. *International journal of informative & futuristic research*, 1 (9).

Merther, C. A. & Charles C. M. (2011). *Educational Research*. USA: Pearson Education, In Polloway Edwards.

Mertler, C. A. (2018). *Introduction to Educational Research* (2nded). Los Angeles, CA: SAGE

Orodho J.A. (2013). Multicultural, Social Studies: The Local History Connection. *Social Studies*, 93 (3), 111-117

Orodho, A.J, (2014). A Hainment of Basic Education for All by 2015, From Rhetoric chimera to practice in Kenya. *International Journal of Current Research (IJCR)*. Vol.6, Issue 01, pp 4666-4674 January 2014

Republic of Kenya (1964) *Kenya Education Commission Report, OmindeReport*, Nairobi, Government Press

Republic of Kenya (1964b), *The Committee on Care and Rehabilitation of the Disabled, NgalaMwendwaReport*, Nairobi, Government Printers

Republic of Kenya (1965b), *Sessional Paper No. 10 of 1965* Nairobi, Government printers.

Republic of Kenya (1976) *Report of the National Committee on Educational Objectives and Policies*, Gachathi Report, Nairobi: Government Press

Republic of Kenya (1988), *'The Presidential Working Party on Education and Manpower – Kamunge Report'*, Nairobi, Government Printers

Republic of Kenya (1999) *'The Commission of Inquiry into the Education System of Kenya - Koech Commission'*, Government Printers, Nairobi

Republic of Kenya (2013). *The basic Education Act 2013*. No 14 2013. Nairobi.

Sharma, K. D. *Topic-Indian Education System And Its Corelation With Teaching And Classroom Authonticity Of Present Modern Scenario.*

..... (2012) *Seven essential components for teacher education for inclusion.*

<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.4324/9780203113585-22/seven-essential-components-teacher-preparation-programs-inclusion>

Srivastiva , M.,de Boer, A,& Pijl, S.J (2015). *Inclusive education in developing Countries: A close look at its Implementation in the last ten years: Education Review. 67: 179-195.*

Teachers role in inclusive education Retrieved from

<https://www.uniassignment.com/essaysamples/education/teachers-role-in-inclusive-education-education-essay.php>.

Teacher preparation for inclusive education: Initial teacher education and in-service professional development. Retrieved from

<http://www.deafeducation.vic.edu.au/Documents/NewsEvents/Lit RevIncTe.pdf>.

Vaughn, Sharon. R., Bos. (2012). *Strategies for Teaching Students with Learning and Behavior Problems*. Retrieved from <https://www.pearson.com/us/higher-education/program/Vaughn-Strategies-for-TeachingStudents-with-Learning-and-Behavior-Problems-Enhanced-Pearson-e-Text-with-Loose>

Walton G. (2015). Tracy's Story: Successful Inclusion in a South Africa School. *SAAED, News*, 30(2), 11-15

World Declaration on Education for All and Framework. Retrieved from unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0012/001275/127583e.pdf